

DEVELOPMENT OF MATHEMATICAL CONCEPTS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN.

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada matematik tasvurlarni shakllantirishga oid bilimlar fazoviy tushunchalar asosiy faoliyatlar shakllantirish vositalarini ko`rsatishni takomillashtirish va asosiy jihatlari ajratib ko`rsatish masalarini yoritib ko`rsatamiz.

**Kalitso`zlar:** matematika, fazoviy tasavvurlar, umumlashtirish, predmetlar, kesma, elementar, metodika, psixologik, to`g`ri chiziq

Annotation: In this article, we highlight the problems of improving the presentation of the means of formation of knowledge, spatial concepts, basic activities and distinguishing the main aspects.

Keywords: mathematics, spatial imagination, generalization, subjects, section, elementary, methodology, psychological, straight line

Аннотация: В данной статье мы освещаем проблемы совершенствования изложения средств формирования знаний, пространственных понятий, основных видов деятельности и выделения основных аспектов.

Ключевые слова: математика, пространственное воображение, обобщение, предметы, раздел, элементарный, методология, психологический, прямая

The level of development of mathematical concepts is different for different people. Its formation requires constant training. These exercises are carried out in the family and in preschool education. A concept is the result of differentiating or generalizing objects and events according to some important features. For

example, number, quantity, section, straight line, etc. Preparing preschool children to learn mathematics is recognized as one of the necessary school subjects. The main issue of the theory and methodology of forming elementary mathematical concepts in children is to develop the didactic foundations of forming mathematical concepts in children. Theoretical aspects of the formation of mathematical concepts in children are created on the basis of psychological, pedagogical and other fundamental sciences.

Including:

documents with demonstration programs;

methodological literature;

team and individual work;

formation of elementary mathematical concepts;

it is a pedagogical process based on the all-purpose manifestations of human creative activity. The goal of forming mathematical concepts is not only to teach children mathematics, but also to prepare them for life, to help them find their place in life. In modern mathematics, the theory of sets is used to justify "number", "figure" and other concepts. Working with children begins with teaching them to select and group things based on their common features. Preparing children for school consists of forming their ideas about numbers, geometric shapes, space and time. It is not for nothing that interesting problems are given a wide place in mathematical literature. Because they believed that the approach through the game facilitates the educational process. It not only makes it easier, but also increases interest in this subject and encourages the child to learn more deeply. At the same time, mathematics should be fun and interesting for children who do not attend preschool. On the other hand, the simplest mathematical examples and problems should be developed not only for simple cognitive skills, but also for quick thinking, description, and reading skills. Work is to educate children's organization, attention, coordination, as well as perseverance and determination to

achieve goals. It is a means of developing the characteristics of children of preschool age. Finding ways to further improve family upbringing of children of preschool education age, cooperation with parents, strengthening the relationship between family education and social education, employees of preschool education organizations, pedagogues, researchers conducting scientific work in this field and is an important task of stylists. Education of children is a task of state importance. Its correct solution depends on the comprehensive approach to educational work, the complete interaction and unity of actions of educational institutions, family and society. The transition of a preschool child to school education always brings about serious changes in his life, morals, interests and relationships. Therefore, it is necessary to prepare the child for school education in kindergarten or at home, to familiarize him with not so difficult knowledge, understanding, skills and abilities. Family education is effective in all aspects, including ideological, moral, aesthetic, physical and work education. For example: ideological education can be inculcated in a child by telling about national heroes who fought for the development of the country, peace and prosperity of the country in the past, introducing the symbolic symbols of our country, memorizing poems and songs about independence and the country. Also, it is to form a sense of readiness for the defense of the Motherland in our children. In the process of family education, a number of moral aspects of a person are formed, so that no other object of education can produce as high a result as in the family. These include great human qualities such as humanity, kindness, compassion, sympathy, culture of behavior, duty and loyalty, gratitude. The family has an important role in providing aesthetic education to the future generation. Singing songs in the family circle, reading a fairy tale or a work in the family circle, watching and analyzing plays and movies together, forming a culture of dressing, taking care of flowers at home, painting are aspects of the formation of aesthetic education in a child. Parents should be extremely responsible for the physical fitness of their growing children. For example: doing morning physical

exercises together with the child, giving proper and vitaminized food, organizing rest and sleep properly, etc. Contributions Parents are interested in preparing preschool children for school. This is understandable, because it requires constant action, determination, and the ability to achieve results. A child of preschool age is prepared for this new type of work not only in the process of educational activities, but also during the performance of any work assignments. The system of working with the family of preschool educational organizations should have a clear goal and content. It is possible to achieve positive results in the education of children due to skillfully combining the forms of work of preschool educational organizations with parents in a team style and individually, organizing pedagogical campaign work among the general population.

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